

OPINION TOWARDS BLENDED LEARNING AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS AT PERAMBALUR DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The present study has investigated about the opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher educators at Perambalur district. Survey method was conducted on a stratified Random sample of 102 Teacher Educators in Perambalur District. Result found that there is no significant difference in the level of Opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their Gender. Male and Female Teacher Educators are having similar level of Opinion towards Blended Learning. Also, there is a significant difference in the level of Opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their Locality of the College. Teacher Educators working in Rural College are having significantly higher level of Opinion towards Blended Learning than the Teacher Educators working in Urban College.

Introduction:

The rapid advancement in information technology (IT) has made remarkable changes in the traditional educational systems. It adopts modern technology and pedagogical techniques in teaching-learning process and creates a learning environment that motivates the students for better learning. Such a system of learning is mainly based on internet services which facilitate active learning. It disseminates different types of information needed for the holistic development of an individual. Blended learning has emerged as an effective method of learning to meet the needs of students' learning style. The growth of blended learning environments in education has emphasized the need for better ways of describing and recognizing good teaching that promotes students learning in this environment. Blended learning combines online components with the conventional face-to-face components that optimize best practices in teaching and learning through synchronous and asynchronous learning environments.

"Education is not the amount of information that is put into your brain and runs riots, then undigested all your life. We must here life building man making and character making assimilation of idea."

- **Swami Vivekananda**

Need of the Study:

The newborn infant is a helpless human being. He has neither any friend nor an enemy. He is not aware of the social customs and traditions. Not only this, he is influenced by the informal and formal agencies of education. But as he grows order, he is influenced by the informal and formal agencies of education. In this way, he develops a sense of responsibility like successfully. In short, education is able to instill in the child a sense of maturity and responsibility by bringing in him the desired changes according to his needs and demands of ever changing society of which he is an integral part.

Blended Learning:

Blended Learning is a term sequentially increasingly used to elaborate the way electronic learning is being merging with traditional classroom methods and independent study to create a new, hybrid technology methodology. It represents a much greater change in basic technique than simply adding computers to classrooms; it represents, in many cases, a fundamental change in the way of teachers and students approach in learning experience. It has already produced an offshoot – the flipped classroom – that has quickly become a distinct approach of its shown.

Sampling Technique Used:

The present study is adopted with the Random Sampling Technique. Random Sampling is generally the best and simplest way to draw a sample from a population. This method of sampling comes under the probabilistic approach. This method is a subset of individuals (a sample) that are chosen from a larger set (a population).

Population of the Study:

In this study, all the teacher educators working in Educational institutions at various B.Ed colleges irrespective of the nature of management and other criteria but located in Perambalur District, Tamil Nadu have been taken as the population for the study. The overall population of teacher educators at Perambalur district is more than 350. It is impossible to collect details from all the teacher educators. For present study the investigator has collected details from 102 Teacher Educators through Random sampling method.

Sample Design and Size:

A good sample must be representative of the entire population for this study, samples has been collected using random sampling technique. The investigator was selected 102 Teacher Educators for the present study.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the significant difference between the mean values of opinion towards blended learning among teacher educators on the basis of their gender.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference between the mean values of opinion towards blended learning among teacher educators on the basis of their locality of the college.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between the opinion towards blended learning among the teacher educators on the basis of their gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the opinion towards blended learning among the teacher educators on the basis of their locality of the college.

Data Analysis:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in Mean scores on the level of opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their Gender.

Table 1: ‘t’ value between the mean scores on the level of opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their Gender

S.No	Gender	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remark
1	Female	51	82.05	8.43	1.13**	Not Significant
2	Male	51	83.87	7.8		

** - Not Significant at 0.05 level

From the above Table-1 the ‘t’ value, 1.13 is not significant at 0.05 level. It is understood from the result that there is no significant difference in the level of Opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their Gender. Male and Female Teacher Educators are having similar level of Opinion towards Blended Learning.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in Mean scores on the level of opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their Locality of the College

Table 2: ‘t’ value between the mean scores on the level of opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their locality of the college

S.No	Locality of the College	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remark
1	Rural	44	85.32	6.98	2.69*	Significant
2	Urban	58	81.17	8.54		

* - Significant at 0.05 level

From the above 2, the ‘t’ value, 2.69 is significant at 0.05 level. It is understood from the result that there is a significant difference in the level of Opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher Educators with respect to their Locality of the College. Teacher Educators working in Rural College are having significantly higher level of Opinion towards Blended Learning than the Teacher Educators working in Urban College.

Findings of the Study:

- The following are the findings of the study.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the level of opinion towards blended learning among teacher educators with respect to their Gender. Male and Female teacher educators are having similar level of opinion towards blended learning.
- ✓ There is a significant difference in the level of opinion towards blended learning among teacher educators with respect to their Locality of the college. Teacher educators working in Rural College are having significantly higher than the teacher educators working in Urban College.

Conclusion:

The present study has investigated about the opinion towards Blended Learning among Teacher educators at Perambalur district. The results provide evidence that the opinion towards Blended Learning among teacher educators is high. It should implement in the B.Ed. colleges so that the students and teacher educators would get more knowledge through internet, multimedia and other teaching aids in order to get clarity about the conceptual learning.

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